

Technological Challenges among Human Kinetics Distance Learning Students of Nigerian Universities: An Analysis of Academic Coping Strategies

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Abstract

This study examined the technological challenges experienced by Human Kinetics distance learning students in Nigerian universities. The review highlighted several challenges such as technical issues with the learning platform, limited access to computers, shortage of electricity, poor pedagogical skills, ineffective time management, lack of instant communication, digital divide and poor internet connections. In addition, the results highlighted various coping strategies adopted by the students such as increasing their duration of studies, forming online study groups, and utilizing physical libraries. With technology providing many benefits to human kinetic educators and students' learning experiences. It also assists the students in finding balance between a healthy use of technology and the negative effects it may cause. The findings of this study offer implications for those who are responsible for creating, managing, and delivering Human Kinetics distance learning courses in Nigerian universities. The study establishes the importance of reliable technical infrastructure and access to learning resources for successful completion of the courses. Furthermore, it provides the basis for designing strategies to reduce technological barriers faced by students. The results of this study may also be useful in understanding and supporting the coping strategies adopted by the Human Kinetics distance learning students in Nigerian universities. It was therefore recommended that online academic counsellors should be provided for the learners.

Keyword: Technology, Human kinetics, Coping strategy

Introduction

Technology has helped to advance educational progress, but there are still certain challenges. By offering internet connectivity, equipment like tablets and PCs, and developing programmes to increase computer literacy for both lecturers and students, the majority of distance learning-based schools are demonstrating their support for higher levels of technology in the classroom. The advantages of educational technologies are commonly recognized by instructors, but they frequently find it difficult to integrate new technologies into their classrooms in an efficient and effective way. Technological integration poses serious difficulties for educators at every level, from purchasing new technological equipment to adapting curricula and teaching methods to include new educational resources. Human kinetics is a discipline that focused on the comprehensive practice of human movement and exercise as well as its impact on health and physical performance (Angba and Abass, 2018). In order to research physical activity and health, the curriculum promotes interdisciplinary and interprofessional approaches. The main goal of distant learning is to give student employees a simple way to earn a higher degree. Despite the interconnected benefits, there are obstacles for both learners and suppliers. Because a portion of the Human Kinetics course is practical in nature, the difficulties cannot be overstated. According to Ojo (2009), these difficulties can be divided into social, environmental, institutional, educational, and psychological. Distance learning in Nigeria Universities is mostly hybrid, which allows the students to have an interactive session in form of revisions before examination.

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While they are far apart, technology will tremendously aid both the tutor and the students in receiving information regarding teaching materials and homework. More specifically, technology supports teachers by enabling them to use videos to illustrate the movement skills that students will develop during learning situations. As a result, information regarding the teaching materials for the subject will be easier to transfer and both teachers and students will learn more. Another issue is that not all faculty members recognize the value of incorporating technology into the teaching and learning process (Ogunlela and Ogunleye, 2014). Also, lecturers who are not technological inclined, are a challenge. Therefore, the need to strive to integrate technology in the learning process and directing them to achieve optimal learning goals for the students. Based on students transition from the classroom walls to the boundaries of virtual reality, it is very important that every distance learning based institutions must provide effective online learning so as to deliver quality education and outcomes-based education to students. Sometimes, students are not prepared to embrace the tutor's introduction of technology as a tool for learning. The difficulty for learners is in how well they comprehend how to use technology wisely for educational objectives. If teachers, students, and the institution all support one another, the deployment of technology use in Human Kinetics learning will go well. Video recorders about sports movement techniques, sports-related movies, the internet, and mobile fitness apps are just a few examples of the technology used by human kinetics lecturers in the learning process. These apps can be downloaded from the AppStore. Another challenge is the inadequate faculty support for learners which could also affect students' ability to progress and complete their study (Osafu, 2017). In Agbofa (2012), the student's motivation could be affected due to the less contact between students' peers and tutors as a result of the once in a while face-to-face arrangement. Also, the usage of part-time facilitators tends to pose several instructional challenges to the learners.

In those days, distance learners in Nigeria are largely adults, and parents, suggesting a huge demand on their time. Due to poor economy and the need for many young ones to cater for themselves as well as desire to further their education, many now engaged in distance learning education. The demands of these multiple roles on these distance learners could pose work, academic and life balance-related challenges. Students could have herculean tasks attending to the demands of their personal lives, academic activities and that of their employer. Inability to address all the dictates of the three constituents (life, education, and work) will result in work and life conflict among distance learners. Work, academic and life conflicts further pose high-level stress upon distance learners and ultimately affect their academic performance (Segbenya & Peniana, 2021). Students may be distracted when using technology for academic purposes, making it difficult for them to multitask. In Sharaievskia et al. (2022), learners are not the only ones who experience stress or anxiety when learning to use technology in the classroom, many instructors experienced stress when learning new technology and having to work extra hours too. Teaching students how to use technology efficiently is an integral role of every educator, however, educators need to lead by example when it comes to using technology within the classroom. With technology providing many benefits to educators and students' learning experiences, assisting students in finding a balance between a healthy use of technology and the negative effects it may cause is critical. The use of technologies in higher education classrooms has both positive and negative consequences. Although the positive effects outweigh the negative ones, it is critical that the negatives are not overlooked because they can be detrimental. Distance learners face psychological, socio-religious, and financial challenges as a result of their various personal and family roles and responsibilities (Ojo & Okon, 2019).

Also, the usage of hired facilities belonging to a second circle institution to deliver a university course content also comes with associated institutional-related challenges regarding the suitability of furniture and washrooms, among others, for distance learners (Segbenya et al., 2019). All these challenges could affect the academic performance or outcomes of distance learners. The face-to-face tutorial and the dependency on the print media- modules/course material for teaching and learning also come with inherent challenges to the distance learner. Delays in supplying modules or course materials could affect the academic performance of distance learners. Furthermore, distance learners could also face an institutional challenge in the form of delays in resolving student assessment-related challenges and communicating timely feedback on students' continuous assessment. Failure to give feedback on students' continuous assessment can affect distance learners' preparation for their examinations (Agbofa, 2012).

Conceptualization of the problem

Higher education is becoming more and more in demand in Nigeria, which is made worse by problems like the rising expense of educational infrastructure and the government's reduced budget. As a result, online education is now viewed as an urgent solution. Even though it can provide convenience, flexibility, and affordability, using technology is also linked to a number of problems, particularly in Nigeria.

Theoretical Perspectives to the problem

Benefits of using technology for online teaching and learning

Across the globe, the higher education system is now transformed to a world where extreme usage of tablets and social media is very common for both teaching as well as learning. According to Angeli & Valanides (2013), technology has played and continues to play an important role in the development and expansion of online education. The way we use technology for teaching and learning has enhanced our education and also proved to have a positive impact on the education process. This adoption of technology has enriched the popularity for Open and Distance Learning (ODL) among learners as it offers flexibility and accessibility. Barbour and Kennedy (2014) found that online teaching encouraged teachers to adopt a new role of facilitators, assisting students to develop problem solving skills, stressing critical thinking, and encouraging collaborative interaction among students. Similarly, ODL lecturers also found that the usage of technology can improve the interaction as well as collaboration among learners. Technologies assist in handling large number of students from different parts of the world and hence at an institutional level, learning using technologies may be considered as a cost-effective teaching method (Botham & Mason, 2007). Technologies can transform higher education in many ways: Digital technology enables fundamental shifts in instructional methods, content and assessment (Weir, & Connor, 2009). The benefits of using technology for online teaching and learning are well documented in literature. Some of them are:

1. **Learn at own pace:** Open and Distance Learning offers the learners the opportunity to study at their own pace. According to Sargent & Casey, (2019), students report benefits of using learning technologies such as the ability to learn at their own pace, to learn independently and to have fun. With the help of technology for online teaching and learning the materials can now be accessed from a computer or from mobile devices. This has created more opportunities for the learners.
2. **Promotes interaction:** Technology offers the opportunities to promote interaction between learners, learners and lecturers as well as with experts in ODL. Nowels & Hewit, (2018), reported that interaction can increase learning and lessen the psychological distance involved in ODL. Similarly, interactions can help in achieving the learning outcomes and thus ensure successful learning. Interaction in turn can promote students' motivation and can enhance the whole learning process. According to Croxto (2014) online courses with high levels of interactivity lead to higher levels of student motivation, improved learning outcomes, and satisfaction over less interactive learning environments.
3. **Promotes higher-order think skills:** Technology tends to promote critical thinking and problem-solving skills among learners. There are many platforms that can be maximized by lectures for the sake of critical learning. Such include: Google Docs, Telegram, Google meet, Microsoft team and Discussion Forums among others. (Moralista & Oducado, 2020).
4. **Opportunities for real-time student assessment:** Technology allows continuous monitoring of the learners' progress in terms of reading, participation in discussion forums and even the amount of time spent on the virtual learning platforms. Digital technology makes it possible to monitor how long students devote to readings and videos, where they get electronic resources, and how quickly they master key concepts (West, 2012).

Empirical Perspectives to the problem

Challenges faced in online teaching and learning in Africa

1. **Access to technology:** Access to technology is also a challenge, especially in many parts of Africa. The underdeveloped areas, as in other countries on the African continent, face challenges in accessing information technology as a result of poor infrastructure (Bandalaria, 2019).
2. **Digital Divide:** When compared with other countries of the world, digital divide in Africa is a main constraint. This is major barrier for the usage of technology for online teaching and learning.
3. **Pedagogical skills:** Online lecturers need to acquire relevant skills to teach online, they are also challenged to develop curricula of an exploratory nature that engages learners with hands-on, inquiry-based learning.
4. **Ineffective Time Management:** Effective time management can be difficult in a distance learning environment, where students are challenged to pace themselves without the support from friends and peers that would help them stay focused in class.
5. **Lack of Instant Communication:** In a conventional university, communication occurs instantly, making it simple for students to ask clarification on unclear subjects and receive replies. Communication is frequently asynchronous in an e-learning environment, which causes a chasm between the teacher and the learner. Sometimes these gaps might lead to misunderstandings, which can cause a problem to worsen before it can be addressed.

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6. **Not Receiving Timely Feedback:** One of the most significant and impactful ways that an instructor interacts with a student is by giving feedback. Students may feel confused or unsure about their goals, their progress, and their performance in the course if feedback is delayed by additional days or weeks due to an online format.
7. **Not Receiving Clear Instructions or Expectations:** It's always crucial to set clear expectations for students. Otherwise, they can only guess at whether they're performing tasks and projects correctly. While setting clear standards is a challenge in any classroom, asynchronous communication can make it a greater obstacle.

Practical Solutions to Challenges faced in online teaching and learning

Here are four steps that teachers can take to help position e-learners for greater success in the virtual classroom.

1. **Time Organization:** Effective time management is a fundamental skill for distance learners. Facilitators should encourage their learners to take advantage of the numerous time management apps and resources that are available to e-learners, they are mostly free. These include daily planner worksheets, infographics, and even a time management calculator. Education experts also recommend periodically surveying the students, which provides one with actionable insights into how the students allocate their time toward various tasks. Guidance can be done too.
2. **Utilize Educational Technology:** Just because communication occurs over the internet doesn't mean it has to be lagged or asynchronous. In fact, there are countless free tools to help students and tutors communicate in real-time. For example, video conferencing software can be used to have live conversations with the students, either one-on-one or in group settings. This gives the students a chance to ask questions, raise concerns, and work through complex course material more successfully. In addition to video conferencing software, instant messaging apps can be used for students who prefer to communicate via text. Examples include Skype, Google Meet, FaceTime, Zoom, and Google Hangouts.
3. **Increase Peer Review:** For students to assess their performance and make improvements, they require prompt, insightful feedback. The feedback that students receive can be enhanced in a number of ways. One strategy is to arrange one-on-one or group meetings with them, for instance, once a week or twice a month, during which you'll provide them feedback on recent work. Allowing the students to give feedback on each other's work more frequently is an additional strategy.
4. **Provide Clear Grading Rubrics:** Rubrics and syllabi are important tools in the traditional classroom. The facilitators should maximize it in the virtual classroom too. Be sure to provide the students with a clear and detailed overview of the course, including information about:
 - a. Resource materials
 - b. Learners' materials
 - c. Mode of grading assignment
 - d. How to share or upload documents
 - e. Solutions to technical issues
 - f. Deadlines, exam dates, days off, and other special calendar events
 - g. Facilitators contact

Emerging technologies that can be used for online teaching and learning in Human Kinetics

Usage of technology in ODL teaching and learning has become very crucial nowadays. In the initial days of ODL the common technologies used for communication were emails and bulletin boards; these are now replaced with synchronous technologies such as mobile technologies, smart board and social media. In 21st century, there has been the replacement of physical textbooks with e-books (offline and online), tablets and ipads. Usage of social media for teaching and learning is also gaining popularity in ODL. Similarly, remote classrooms enhanced by video images (video conferencing), shared writing and display spaces (smartboards), and feedback mechanisms including polling and text chat (web conferencing) are very common in ODL (Anderson & Dron, 2012).

Theoretical review of coping strategies

Coping strategies are defined as methods employed by people to deal with situations that require a tremendous investment of their resources such as time and effort. Coping strategy can be reviewed based on the following theory:

1. **Transactional Coping Theory:** The transactional coping theory helps to discuss how and why individuals need to manage different circumstances and cope with challenges associated with situations.
2. **Emotional- focused Coping Strategy:** Emotion-focused coping refers to efforts to reduce the impact of emotional stressors. On the other hand, emotion-focused coping strategies deploy several tactics to mitigate or reduce related

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emotional stress produced by the problem. Even though both coping strategies are used in most stressful encounters, they depend on how one appraises the situation (Schwarzer & Knoll, 2007). When we are emotionally stressed, we may feel overwhelmed by feelings such as fear, anger, sadness, or shame. We may even feel numb or “spaced out,” with either too much or too little emotional response to the situation. In the process of coping with emotional stressors, there is need to regulate one’s emotions in various ways. Identify what is behind your feelings so that they don’t feel so overwhelming. Also, an individual must try to accept his/her feelings so as to avoid pushing them away, as well as reduce the intensity of the feelings through distraction or relaxation.

Emotion-focused coping can be positive or negative. Positive examples include talking or writing about their emotions through therapy or journaling, mindful meditation, or distraction with other activities.

Benefits of using emotion-focused coping

1. Emotion-focused coping is flexible. Emotion-focused coping gives you the tools to change your emotional response as needed. You might start out feeling overwhelmed and end up feeling calm. You might start out feeling too little and end up feeling energized.
2. Emotion-focused coping can be a good strategy to use before working on problem-focused techniques.
3. Emotion-focused coping can be helpful for all kinds of stressors.

Disadvantages of using emotion-focused coping

1. People with low emotional intelligence may find it difficult to be aware of and change their feelings.
2. Getting overwhelmed by altering feelings.
3. Getting to a new level of acceptance that is not helpful based on acceptance.

Problem-based focus coping strategy

Problem-focused coping refers to efforts to solve the underlying causes of stress. The problem-focused coping strategies relate to a situation where individuals solve the relevant external problem and include a problem-oriented approach aimed at the self (Kwaah & Essilfie, 2017). When we are stressed by a problem or challenge, we feel like we’re not in control of our lives and that we’re not going to be able to meet our goals. When trying to cope with these stressors, we may attempt to generate solutions and new ways of approaching the problem. You might try to reduce the intensity of your feelings by talking to an objective friend, brainstorming different solutions, or writing down your emotions to get them out of your head. Problem-focused coping has been shown to promote mental health, provide a sense of control as well as reduce depression, paranoid thinking, anxiety and aggression.

Uses of problem-focused coping

1. If there is need to solve the underlying causes of stress, then problem-focused coping will be more effective.
2. Problem-focused coping is a good choice when an individual want to feel in control of ones life and have a solid plan for solving the underlying causes of the stress.
3. Problem-focused coping has a positive effect on individuals’ mood.
4. Problem-focused coping can help reduce some of the negative impacts of stress.

Some weaknesses of problem-focused coping

1. Problem-focused coping doesn’t always reduce the intensity of one’s feelings.
2. Problem-focused coping can make one feel stressed about the challenges of solving the problems.

Institutionally related challenges and academic output of distance learners

Another challenge distance learners face is institutionally related challenges that manifest themselves in five main forms: infrastructure or study centre-related challenges, delay in supplying course materials, quality and calibre of course facilitators, delay in resolving students’ assessment-related challenges, internet or technology-related challenges for online courses (Segbenya & Peniana, 2021). Learners’ challenges regarding infrastructure borders on classroom furniture and washrooms. Distance educational institutions do not have their own permanent built facilities hosting their distance programmes in the various districts (Segbenya & Peniana, 2021). For this reason, they relied on franchised facilities or

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infrastructure/study centres in various communities to roll out their distance programmes. Most of these facilities are somewhat below the standard existing on regular campuses. The most extensive challenges distance learners have in these hired facilities are poor sanitary conditions and uncomfortable furniture in the classrooms, making sitting down for a long time during face-to-face sessions very challenging for distance learners (Segbenya et al., 2019).

Delay in printing course materials could be responsible for late distribution of modules to distance learners (Bampo, 2008; Osafo, 2017) found subletting the production function of modules to private entities as a cause of delay in supplying course materials to distance students. Such delays have the potential of impacting on students' performance and satisfaction with academic programmes (Segbenya & Peniana, 2021). Distance learners also have several challenges with the calibre of course facilitators appointed by the various institutions to handle such courses (Fricke, 2010). The part-time tutors are sometimes not committed to the distance programmes and are not of the same qualification as their counterparts in the regular stream (Segbenya & Nyieku, 2021; Mamhute, 2011). The commitment and qualification differences could affect tutors' delivery of course materials and could also affect distance learners' ability to do well in their academic programmes. Thus, institutional related factors could have effect on educational output and the coping mechanisms adopted by distance learners.

Conclusion

The challenges that have been identified in this study include challenges that come from the environment (availability of facilities & infrastructure supporting technology integration), teachers, students, and other school community support are some of the challenges that must be faced by all person that concerned to be able to integrate technology into learning. The challenge of using technology in Physical Education learning can be a platform for formulating solutions that can be used in overcoming problems of using technology in the Physical Education teaching and learning process.

Recommendations

1. Face-to-face counselling could be supplemented with electronic or online counselling sessions to cover every distance learner to enable them to obtain good grades, complete their academic programmes on time, and enhance their satisfaction level for the distance education programme pursued.
2. There should be decent and suitable teaching and learning facilities for face-to-face sessions, if need arises, most especially for practical classes.
3. There is need for continuous in-service training for the course facilitators so as to update their technological skills and teaching methodology.

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